

COMPLEX TEMPORAL FUZZY SOFT INTERIOR IDEALS OVER SEMIGROUPS

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Abstract:

In this paper, we introduce the notion of Complex temporal fuzzy soft semi groups (CTFSG) and its Cartesian product with the help of suitable example, also we define direct product, ideals and prove some results.

Key Words: Soft Set, Fuzzy Soft Set, Temporal Fuzzy Set, Left Ideal, Interior Ideal, Union and Intersection

1. Introduction:

The theory of fuzzy sets proposed by L.A. Zadeh [1965] in 1965, has achieved a great success in various fields. In 1999, Molodtsov [1999] introduced the concept of soft sets, which can be seen as a new mathematical tool for dealing with uncertainties. This so-called soft set theory is free from the difficulties affecting existing methods. Presently, works on soft set theory are progressing rapidly. Maji et al. [2002] defined several operations on soft sets and made a theoretical study on the theory of soft sets. Atagün and Sezgin [2016] defined the concepts of soft sub rings and ideals of a ring, soft subfields of a field and soft sub modules of a module and studied their related properties with respect to soft set operations. Also union soft sub structures of near-rings and near-ring modules are studied in [2012]. Maji et al. [2002] presented the concept of the fuzzy soft sets (fs-sets) by embedding the ideas of fuzzy sets [2007]. By using this definition of fs-sets many interesting applications of soft set theory have been expanded by some researchers. Roy and Maji [2003] gave some applications of fs-sets. Aktas. And Cagman [2007] compared soft sets with the related concepts of fuzzy sets and rough sets. In this paper we introduce the notion of Complex temporal fuzzy soft semi groups (CTFSG) and its cartesian product with the help of suitable example, Also we define direct product, ideals and prove some results.

2. Preliminaries:

In this section, we recall basic definitions of soft set theory that are useful for subsequent sections. For more detail see the papers [1999].

Through out the paper, U refers to an initial universe, E is a set of parameters and $P(U)$ is the power set of U . \subset and \supset stand for proper subset and super set, respectively.

Definition 2.1: For any subset A of E , a soft set λ_A over U is a set, defined by a function λ_A , representing the mapping $\lambda_A: E \rightarrow P(U)$. A soft set over U can also be represented by the set of ordered pairs $\lambda_A = \{(x, \lambda_A(x)); x \in E, \lambda_A(x) \in P(U)\}$. Note that the set of all soft sets over U will be denoted by $S(U)$.

Definition 2.2: Let $\lambda, \mu \in S(U)$. Then

- ✓ If $\lambda(e) = \emptyset$ for all $e \in E$, λ is said to be a null soft set, denoted by \emptyset .
- ✓ If $\lambda(e) = U$ for all $e \in E$, λ is said to be an absolute soft set, denoted by U .
- ✓ λ is a soft subset of μ , denoted $\lambda \subseteq \mu$, if $\lambda(e) \subseteq \mu(e)$ for all $e \in E$.
- ✓ Soft union of λ and μ , denoted by $\lambda \cup \mu$, is a soft set over U and defined by $\lambda \cup \mu: E \rightarrow P(U)$ such that $(\lambda \cup \mu)(e) = \lambda(e) \cup \mu(e)$ for all $e \in E$.
- ✓ $\lambda = \mu$, if $\lambda \subseteq \mu$ and $\lambda \supseteq \mu$.
- ✓ Soft intersection of λ and μ , denoted by $\lambda \cap \mu$, is a soft set over U and defined by $\lambda \cap \mu: E \rightarrow P(U)$ such that $(\lambda \cap \mu)(e) = \lambda(e) \cap \mu(e)$ for all $e \in E$.
- ✓ Soft complement of λ is denoted by λ^c and defined by $\lambda^c: E \rightarrow P(U)$ such that $\lambda^c(e) = U/\lambda(e)$ for all $e \in E$.

Definition 2.3: Let E be a parameter set, $S \subset E$ and $\lambda: S \rightarrow E$ be an injection function. Then $S \cup \lambda(s)$ is called extended parameter set of S and denoted by ξ_S . If $S=E$, then extended parameter set of S will be denoted by ξ .

Definition 2.4: A temporal fuzzy set is an object of the form $A(T) = \{h(x, t), \mu_A(x, t) : (x, t) \in E \times T\}$ where (a) $A \subset E$ is a fixed set (b) $0 \leq \mu_A(x, t) \leq 1$ for every $(x, t) \in E \times T$. (c) $\mu_A(x, t)$ are the degrees of membership of the element $x \in E$ at the time-moment $t \in T$.

Example 2.5: Suppose that is a temporal fuzzy set (Table 1) defined on $= \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$ with respect to the time moment set $= \{t_1, t_2\}$:

Table 1: Temporal fuzzy set A

t/x	t ₁	t ₂
x ₁	0.2	0.5
x ₂	1.0	0.7

x_3	0.5	0.4
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Definition 2.6: A Complex temporal I fuzzy soft set $C = \{ \langle Pc . e^{i\delta c} \rangle \}$ on a semi group S is known as a Complex temporalfuzzy soft left ideal of S, if $C(xy,t) \geq C(y,t)$. i.e.,

$$Pc(xy,t) . e^{i\delta c(xy,t)} \geq Pc(y,t) e^{i\delta c(x,t)} \text{ for all } x,y \in S \text{ and } t \in T$$

Example 2.7: Let $S = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ be a semigroup with the following multiplication table.

•	1	2	3	4
1	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	1	1
3	1	1	2	1
4	1	1	2	2

Consider a Complex temporal fuzzy soft set C on S are: $C = \{ \langle 1, 0.3 e^{0.7\pi i} \rangle, \langle 1, 0.3 e^{0.8\pi i} \rangle, \langle 1, 0.3 e^{0.6\pi i} \rangle, \langle 1, 0.3 e^{0.3\pi i} \rangle \}$ then C is a complex temporalfuzzy left ideal of S.

Definition 2.8: A Complex temporal fuzzy soft set $C = \{ \langle Pc . e^{i\delta c} \rangle \}$ on a semi group S is known as a complex temporal fuzzy soft right ideal of S, if $C(xy,t) \geq C(x,t)$, i.e., $Pc(xy,t) . e^{i\delta c(xy,t)} \geq Pc(x,t) e^{i\delta c(x,t)}$ for all $x,y \in S$ and $t \in T$.

Definition 2.9: A Complex temporal fuzzy soft set $C = \{ \langle Pc . e^{i\delta c} \rangle \}$ on a semi group S is known as a complex temporalfuzzy soft right ideal of S, if it both a complex temporal fuzzy soft left ideal of S, if it both a complex temporal fuzzy soft left ideal and a complex temporal fuzzy soft right ideal of S.

Example 2.10: Let $S = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ be a semigroup with the following Cayle table.

•	1	2	3
1	1	1	1
2	1	1	1
3	1	1	3

Consider a Complex temporal fuzzy soft set C on S as: $C = \{ \langle 1, 0.7 e^{0.7\pi i} \rangle, \langle 2, 0.3 e^{0.2\pi i} \rangle, \langle 3, 0.4 e^{0.7\pi i} \rangle \}$ then obviously C is a complex temporal fuzzy soft ideal of S.

Remark 2.11: Every Complex temporal fuzzy soft left (resp., right) ideal is a complex temporal fuzzy soft semi group. But the Converse may not be true as seen in the following example.

Example 2.12: Let $S = \{a, b, c, d\}$ be a semigroup with the following Cayle table.

•	a	b	c	d
a	a	a	a	a
b	a	a	a	a
c	a	a	a	b
d	a	a	b	c

Consider a Complex temporal fuzzy soft set C on S as: $C = \{ \langle a, 0.8 e^{0.6\pi i} \rangle, \langle b, 0.6 e^{0.6\pi i} \rangle, \langle c, 0.8 e^{0.5\pi i} \rangle, \langle d, 0.4 e^{0.4\pi i} \rangle \}$ then obviously C is a complex temporal fuzzy soft semi group, however it is not a right ideal of S, because $\mu_c(cd) = \mu_c(b) = 0.6 e^{0.6\pi i}$ (not \geq) $0.8 e^{0.5\pi i} = \mu_c(c)$

Definition 2.13 : A Complex temporal fuzzy soft set on a semi group S is known as a complex temporal I fuzzy soft interior ideal of S, if $C(xky,y) \geq C(k,t)$

$$\text{i.e.) } Pc(xky,t) . e^{i\delta c(xky,t)} \geq Pc(k,t) e^{i\delta c(kx,t)} \text{ for all } x,k, y \in S \text{ and } t \in T.$$

Example 2.14: Let $S = \{a, b, c, d\}$ be a semigroup then

•	a	b	c	d
a	a	a	a	a
b	a	a	a	a
c	a	a	b	a
d	a	a	b	

$C = \{ \langle a, 0.7 e^{0.6\pi i} \rangle, \langle b, 0.3 e^{0.7\pi i} \rangle, \langle c, 0.3 e^{0.7\pi i} \rangle, \langle d, 0.0 e^{0.0\pi i} \rangle \}$ then obviously C is a complex temporal fuzzy soft interior ideal of S.

Remark 2.15: Every Complex temproual fuzzy soft interior ideal is a complex temporal fuzzy soft interior ideal. But the converse may not be true as seen in the above example. For

Left Ideal: $\mu_c(dc,t) = \mu_c(b,t) = 0$ (not \geq) $0.3 e^{0.7\pi i} = \mu_c(c,t)$

Right ideal: $\mu_c(dc,t) = \mu_c(b,t) = 0 \geq \mu_c(d)$ So it is a Complex temporal fuzzy soft right ideal but not a left ideal.

Hence C is not a Complex temporal fuzzy soft ideal. ⊗

3. Results:

The following results based on the above definitions

Proposition 3.1: A complex temporal fuzzy soft set C on a semi group S, the following are equivalent;

- ✓ C is a Complex temporal fuzzy soft ideal of S.

✓ $S \otimes C \subseteq C$.

Proof:

(i) \Rightarrow (ii)

Assume that C is a complex temporal fuzzy soft ideal of S .

Let $x \in S$, and $t \in T$, such that $(S \otimes C)(x,t) = 0$; then it is clear $S \otimes C \subseteq C$, whenever there exist any two element $y,k \in S$ such that $x = yk$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Then } (Is \bullet Pc \bullet e^{i\delta_c})(x,t) &= \max_{(x=yk)} [\inf \{ Is(y,t) \bullet Pc(k,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(k,t)} \} \\ &\leq \max_{(x=yk)} [\inf \{ I \bullet e^{i2\pi} \bullet Pc(yk,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(yx,t)} \} \\ &= Pc(x,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(x,t)} \end{aligned}$$

(ii) \Rightarrow (i)

Suppose $S \otimes C \subseteq C$. For any element $y,k \in S$, let $x = yk$, then

$$\begin{aligned} Pc(yk,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(yk,t)} &= Pc(k,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(x,t)} \\ &\geq \{ Is \bullet Pc \bullet e^{i\delta_c} \}(x,t) \\ &= \max_{(x=yk)} [\inf \{ Is(y,t) \bullet Pc(k,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(k,t)} \} \\ &= Pc(x,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(x,t)} \end{aligned}$$

Hence C is a Complex temporal fuzzy soft left ideal of S .

Proposition 3.2: A Complex temporal fuzzy soft set C on a semi group S , the following are equivalent.

✓ C is a complex temporal right ideal of S .

✓ (ii) $C \otimes_S \subseteq C$.

Proof:

Proof is similar to the proposition 3.1

Theorem 3.3: If C is a Complex temporal fuzzy soft set of a semi group S . Then $S \otimes C$ (resp. $C \otimes S$) is a complex temporal fuzzy soft left (resp. Right) ideal of S .

Proof:

$$\text{Since } S \otimes (S \otimes C) = (S \otimes S) \otimes C \subseteq S \otimes C$$

It follows from proposition 3.1, that $S \otimes C$ is a complex temporal fuzzy soft left ideal of S . Similarly $C \otimes S$ is a complex temporal fuzzy soft right ideal of S .

Theorem 3.4: Let S be a left zero semigroup of S . If C is a complex temporal fuzzy soft left ideal of S , then $C(x,t) = C(y,t)$ for all $x,y \in S$ and $t \in T$.

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } x,y \in S \text{ and } t \in T \text{ then } xy=x \text{ and } yx=y \text{ then} \\ Pc(x,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(x,t)} &= Pc(xy,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(xy,t)} \\ &\geq Pc(y,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(y,t)} \\ &= Pc(yx,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(yx,t)} \\ &= Pc(x,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(x,t)} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $C(x,t) = C(y,t)$ for all $x,y \in S$ and $t \in T$.

Theorem 3.5: Let S be a right zero semigroup of S . If C is a complex temporal fuzzy soft right ideal of S , then $C(x,t) = C(y,t)$ for all $x,y \in S$ and $t \in T$.

Proof:

Proof is similar to the theorem 3.4.

Theorem 3.6: Let C be a complex temporal fuzzy soft left ideal of a semigroup S . If the set of idempotent elements of S form a left zero semi group of S , then $C(x,t) = C(y,t)$ for all idempotent elements x and y of S and $t \in T$.

Proof:

Let $\text{Idm}(S)$ be the set of all idempotent elements of S and assume that $\text{Idm}(S)$ is a left zero semigroup of S .

For any $x,y \in \text{Idm}(S)$ and $t \in T$,

We have $xy = x$ and $yx = y$ then

$$\begin{aligned} Pc(x,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(x,t)} &= Pc(xy,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(xy,t)} \\ &\geq Pc(y,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(y,t)} \\ &= Pc(yx,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(yx,t)} \\ &= Pc(x,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(x,t)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\geq Pc(x,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(x,t)} \\ &= Pc(y,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_c(y,t)} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $C(x,t) = C(y,t)$ for all $x,y \in \text{Idm}(S)$ and $t \in T$.

Proposition 3.7: If S be a semi group, then the intersection of two complex temporal fuzzy soft left (respectively right) ideal of S is a Complex temporal fuzzy soft left (respectively right) ideal of S .

Proof:

Let C_1 and C_2 be any two complex temporal fuzzy soft left ideal of semigroup S , and $x, y \in S$ and $t \in T$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} (Pc_1 \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_1}} \cap Pc_2 \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_2}})(xy,t) &= \inf \{ Pc_1(xy,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_1}(xy,t)}, Pc_2(xy,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_2}(xy,t)} \} \\ &\geq \inf \{ Pc_1(y,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_1}(y,t)}, Pc_2(xy,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_2}(xy,t)} \} \\ &= \{ Pc_1 \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_1}}, Pc_2 \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_2}} \}(y,t) \end{aligned}$$

Thus $C_1 \cap C_2$ is a complex temporal fuzzy soft left ideal of S .

Proposition 3.8: If S be a semi group, then the union of two Complex temporal fuzzy soft left (resp right) ideals of S is a complex temporal fuzzy soft left (respectively right) ideal of S .

Proof:

Let C_1 and C_2 be any two complex temporal fuzzy soft left ideals of S , and $x,y \in S$, and $t \in T$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (Pc_1 \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_1}} \cup Pc_2 \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_2}})(xy,t) &= \sup \{ Pc_1(xy,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_1}(xy,t)}, Pc_2(xy,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_2}(xy,t)} \} \\ &\geq \sup \{ Pc_1(y,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_1}(y,t)}, Pc_2(xy,t) \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_2}(xy,t)} \} \\ &= \{ Pc_1 \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_1}} \cap Pc_2 \bullet e^{i\delta_{c_2}} \}(y,t) \end{aligned}$$

Thus $C_1 \cup C_2$ is a complex temporal fuzzy soft left ideal of S .

Theorem 3.9: If C_1 and C_2 be a complex temporal fuzzy soft left and right ideals of a semi group S , respectively, then $C_1 \otimes C_2 \subseteq C_1 \cap C_2$

Proof:

Let C_1 is complex temporal fuzzy soft right ideal and C_2 is any complex temporal fuzzy soft left ideal of S , then by proposition 3.1 and proposition 3.2, we have

$$C_1 \otimes C_2 \subseteq C_1 \otimes S \subseteq C_1 \text{ and } C_1 \otimes C_2 \subseteq S \otimes C_2$$

Conclusion:

In this paper, we define Complex temporal fuzzy soft left (respectively right) ideal in semi group and study some results prove on its.

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